

A MULTIFACTOR ECONOMETRICAL ASSESSMENT OF POVERTY REDUCTION

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada kambaғallichi qisqartirishning kўp omilli ekonometrik baғolash usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi.

Kalit sozlar: Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy soҳa. Iqtisodiy institutlar. Kambaғallichi qisqartirish. Ishsizlik darajasi. Real daromad.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются методы многофакторной эконометрической оценки сокращения бедности.

Ключевые слова: Социально-экономическая сфера. Экономические институты. Сокращение бедности. Уровень безработицы. Реальный доход.

Resume: The article discusses methods of multivariate econometric assessment of poverty reduction.

Key words: Socio-economic sphere. Economic institutions. Poverty reduction. Unemployment rate. Real income.

Enter. At present, as in the whole world, the effectiveness of economic reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its territories is also being evaluated low of poverty spread , employment of the crisis to deepen , man potential repeat work release to the narrowing of the population health and life of quality deterioration take is coming This while own in turn citizens human , labor and intellectual potential to develop threat puts _

Socio-economic in the field many problems , including population _ marriage level increase poverty _ overcome for Uzbekistan to the Republic perfect to mechanisms have new , more effective institutions need _ This about each one society state and citizens by work developed and efficient supported economic and political the rules set within activity conduct to the goal is appropriate . Economical institutions better education get , save and investing , new _ technologies current reach and others like economic incentives determines _ But political process of people which economic institutions under to live defines and political of institutions himself this process how the passing of determines _

Exactly therefore for society social protection in doing higher education care expand system current reach today's in the day Uzbekistan in the Republic necessary , it is socio-economic to dangers answer to give able and of society all in groups poor population to reduce help gives _ Next stages to determine for state policy improvement mathematical modeling in order to and forecasting method use necessary _

Method. To poverty effect doer main from indicators one this of the population income is , therefore for their to change effect doer factors as well as income increase or decrease trend learning need _ This problem learning for Uzbekistan Republic of less provided (poverty) level - Yr to change effect doer , population soul per head main to capital capitalized investment -X1, in the republic unemployment level -X2, of the population of the republic to

live minimum – X3, population soul per head total real income is X4 and higher to education coverage level – X5 indicators was selected .

Above given designations based on take went research from the result come came out without initially conducted correlative analysis results positive and multicollinearity is available that it is not was determined . Then , Eviews from the program used without determined and all criteria based on right and adequate that found Uzbekistan in the Republic less level of prosperity (poverty). to change a lot from the factorial regression equation :

$$Y_r = \frac{x_2^{0.077} \cdot x_3^{2.13}}{x_1^{0.67} \cdot x_4^{0.2672} x_4^{0.13} \cdot e_3^{1.51}}$$

and this in Eq participation reached when t=23 of the factors to time related trend equations from system :

- population soul per head main to capital capitalized investment
X1=616.8+339.9*t;
- unemployment level : X 2=-0.2+0.46*t;
- to live minimum : X 3=33.1+18.5*t;
- population soul per head total real income : X4=-1372.4+668.1*t;
- high to education coverage : X5=10.3+0.9*t .

Conclusion . Quoted formulas system and common from Eq using Uzbekistan in the republic less level of prosperity (poverty). to change a lot factorial forecast is determined (Table 1).

Table from the data apparently by 2027 go Uzbekistan in the republic less poverty level by 2022 ___ compared to 3.8 percent increase to 21.6 % unemployment increased by 2.8%

Table 1

Uzbekistan Republic of less level of prosperity (poverty). to change a lot factor forecasting results

Year	Few provide - hanlik level , %	Population soul per head main to capital capitalized inv., thousand soum	Unemployment level , %	Live minimum a thousand soum	Population soul per head total real income , thousand soum	High to education coverage
2022	17.8	7200.9	10.4	458.6	13993.9	31
2023	18.5	7540.8	10.8	477.1	14662	31.9
2024	19.3	7880.7	11.3	495.6	15330.1	32.8
2025	20.0	8220.6	11.8	514.1	15998.2	33.7
2026	20.8	8560.5	12.2	532.6	16666.3	34.6
2027	21.6	8900.4	12.7	551.1	17334.4	35.5

to reach 12.7% , to live minimum 110 thousand to soum increased to 551.1 thousand to soum reach population soul per head total real income is 4008.5 thousand to soum increased to

17334.4 thousand to soum reach the most the main thing while higher to education coverage and it increased by 5.4% to 35.5% that it is expected let's see can _ This while of the Republic upcoming prospect for in the country population employment provide for new small business entities to open help them _ more wider opportunities to give measures work exit to the goal is appropriate.

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